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CLINICAL FEATURES OF SOME RISK FACTORS FOR STROKE IN WOMEN (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ANNOTATION

Cerebral circulatory disorders (CCD) by prevalence occupy the leading position in the list of the most significant social problems. Stroke is one of the main causes of disability in patients, regardless of age, sex, ethnicity and country of residence. It should be emphasised that the high prevalence of arterial hypertension (AH) and major cardiovascular diseases, such as atherosclerosis (AS) and ischemic heart disease (IHD), along with decreasing life expectancy of patients, lead to a constant increase in the overall structure of cerebrovascular pathology of the proportion of acute forms of NMI, primarily ischemic stroke.

Key words: stroke, women, risk factors, arterial hypertension

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КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ФАКТОРОВ РИСКА РАЗВИТИЯ ИНСУЛЬТА У ЖЕНЩИН (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Нарушения мозгового кровообращения (НМК) по распространенности занимают лидирующее положение в списке наиболее значимых социальных проблем. Инсульт одна из основных причин инвалидизации больных, независимо от возраста, пола, этнической принадлежности и страны проживания. Следует подчеркнуть, что большая распространенность артериальной гипертензии (АГ) и основных сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, таких как атеросклероз (АС) и ишемическая болезнь сердца (ИБС), наряду с уменьшением продолжительности жизни больных, приводят к постоянному увеличению в общей структуре цереброваскулярной патологии удельного веса острых форм НМК, в первую очередь ишемического инсульта .

Ключевые слова: инсульт, женщины, факторы риска, артериальная гипертензия

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**AYOLARDA INSULT RIVOJLANISHIGA OLIB KELADIGAN BA'ZI XAVF
OMILLARINI KLINIK XUSUSIYATLARI (ADABIYOT SHARHI)**

ANNOTATSIYA

Miya qon aylanishining buzilishi (MQB) turli kasalliklar ichida eng muhim ijtimoiy muammolar ro'yxatida yetakchi o'rinni egallaydi. Insult kasalligi yoshi, jinsi, etnik kelib chiqishi va yashash mamlakatidan qat'iy nazar, bemorlarning nogironligining asosiy sabablaridan biridir. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, arterial gipertenziya (AG) va ateroskleroz (AS) va koronar arteriya kasalligi kabi asosiy yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining keng tarqalishi, bemorlarning umr ko'rish davomiyligining pasayishi bilan birga, serebrovaskulyar patologiyaning umumiy tuzilishida o'tkir shakllari, birinchi navbatda, ishemik insultning o'ziga xos og'irligining doimiy o'sishiga olib keladi

Kalit so'zlar: insult, ayollar, xavf omillari, arterial gipertenziya

Introduction. Stroke is 1.25 times more common in men than in women [3,5]. However, due to the longer life expectancy of women, the total number of women who die from stroke is higher [6,10]. Ischemic stroke develops 4 times more often in women and 5 times more often in men than hemorrhagic stroke, with the incidence in men aged 75-80 years exceeding the incidence in women of the corresponding age by 500 cases per 100,000 population [11]. Stroke is the second leading cause of death in the population over 65 years of age, with 60% of all stroke deaths occurring in women (3.2 million deaths per year). In Europe and the USA, cardiovascular disease mortality in women is 1.5 times higher than cancer mortality. More than 500,000 women die from cardiovascular disease in the USA each year, which is approximately 1 death per minute [12].

By 2015, the socioeconomic burden of stroke increased by 22% in terms of mortality and 31% in terms of potential life years lost due to premature death and disability (Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs)). According to recent data, 58% of all stroke cases develop in patients under 70 years of age [2]. At present, there is a large number of studies devoted to the study of the peculiarities of risk factors for stroke development in men and women. However, contradictory literature data, the lack of a unified view on the problem of gender-oriented approach to stroke prevention determines the relevance of the posed problem. Gender is a non-correctable risk factor for stroke development. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) definition, sex is a set of traits by which a specific division of individuals or cells is made, based on their morphological and physiological features and allowing for the combination of parental hereditary traits in offspring in the process of

sexual reproduction. In the literature, there is a terminological distinction between the concepts of "biological sex" and "gender", which is understood as a set of social and behavioral factors in addition to biological affiliation [1,3].

The most significant non-gender-specific risk factors for stroke development are: AH, heart disease, including atrial fibrillation, smoking, disorders of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism, excessive alcohol consumption, excessive body weight, low physical activity and sedentary lifestyle, emotional stress [4]. However, in women, taking into account their reproductive status, the frequency and significance of risk factors are different than in men. Risk factors for the development of ICH that are more common in women than in men include: AH, atrial fibrillation, diabetes mellitus, abdominal obesity, migraine with aura, emotional stress and depression. Factors such as age at menarche, pregnancy, gestational diabetes mellitus, pre-eclampsia, changes in hormonal status, use of combined oral contraceptives and hormone replacement therapy are exclusive to women [6, 7].

Arterial hypertension. The level of both systolic and diastolic blood pressure (BP) is closely associated with the development of stroke [1,8]. The risk of NMI development in patients with BP more than 160/95 mm Hg increases approximately 4 times in comparison with those with normal BP (below 140/90 mm Hg), and at BP more than 200/115 mm Hg. - 10 times. AH is the most important and correctable risk factor for the development of ICH in both men and women. However, the prevalence of AH differs according to age and sex. Thus, AH is more common in men than in women before 60 years of age, while after 60 years of age the prevalence of AH in women is higher than in men (66.5 and 63.1 per cent, respectively). The most frequent form of AH in women is isolated systolic A.H. High systolic BP and increased BP variability after menopause are the main causes of left ventricular hypertrophy, heart failure and stroke [1,9]. According to the NHANES III study, the incidence of AH in women aged 55-56 years is 46-53%, in women aged over 65 years - 68%. According to the results of a survey of a Russian national representative sample standardized by age, the prevalence of AH in men is 39.2%, in women - 41.1% [8]. A screening study among men 40-59 years old showed that BP 160/95 mm Hg and higher is detected in 30% of men 40-49 years old and in 38% of men 50-59 years old. At the same time, 65% of men with AH had BP not exceeding 180/105 mmHg and only 12% had 200/115 mmHg or higher [2].

Atrial fibrillation is detected in a significant proportion of the population and is associated with about 1/2 of all cases of stroke due to thromboembolism from various parts of the heart. The risk of developing atrial fibrillation over the age of 55 years is 23.8% in men and 22.2% in women [3]. However, due to the longer life expectancy of women and the increasing incidence of atrial fibrillation with age, the absolute number of women with atrial fibrillation is greater than men [2, 4]. The CHA2DS2-VASc scale considers "major" and "clinically significant" risk factors for stroke in patients with atrial fibrillation. The "large" factors include ischemic stroke, transient ischemic attacks, history of embolism and age over 75 years. Each "major" factor is rated at 2 points. All other risk factors (cardiovascular disease, age between 65 and 74 years, and female sex) are considered "clinically significant" and each of them is scored 1 point [2, 5].

Smoking increases the risk of stroke by 1.5 times, and quitting smoking is accompanied by a decrease in this risk. After smoking cessation for 2-4 years, the risk of cardiovascular disease decreases 2-fold, but it remains elevated for another 10 years (according to some data - for 20 years) [6]. The prevalence of smoking is higher among men. However, with the same number of cigarettes, smoking has a greater negative effect on women's health [7].

Carbohydrate metabolism disorders. Diabetes mellitus, which is a risk factor for NMI, increases the probability of developing NMI 5 times in women and 2-3 times in men [9]. In addition, the unfavorable role of insulin resistance has been shown, which is observed when the response of insulin-sensitive organs and tissues (liver, muscle, adipose tissue) to the action of insulin at its sufficient concentration is reduced. Insulin resistance leads to decreased glucose uptake by tissues, resulting in hyperglycemia [3,10]. Among stroke patients, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus is 32.5% in women and 32.7% in men [11]. Carbohydrate metabolism disorders often lead to the formation of the so-called metabolic syndrome (MS), which is characterized, along with hyperinsulinaemia, by increased plasma triglycerides, decreased antiatherogenic high-density

lipoproteins (HDL), hypertension and central obesity. In general, the syndrome of multiple metabolic disorders leads to accelerated development of atherosclerosis [12].

The incidence of MS increases progressively 6 years before the onset of menopause and for 6 years after its onset. The rate of this increase is independent of age and other risk factors. Menopausal increase in testosterone activity is the main hormonal factor associated with the development of M.S. A decrease in estrogen levels is an insignificant risk factor for the development of M.S. It is more likely that testosterone has a direct negative effect on the risk of cardiovascular complications [4].

Lipid metabolism disorders. It is known that AS is a significant factor leading to the development of both myocardial infarction and ischemic stroke. Currently, great importance is attached to the assessment of the ratio of individual fractions of lipoproteins: low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and HDL, lipoprotein (a) and triglycerides. Lipid metabolism disorders differ in men and women. In the former, the main significance in atherogenesis is an increased level of LDL, in the latter, a decrease in HDL is more important. Cholesterol (CH) levels are lower in women at a young age than in men of the same age. During menopause, the levels of HC and LDL increase by 10 and 14% respectively [3,5].

Alcohol. Excessive alcohol consumption (more than 60 g of ethanol per day) increases the risk of stroke [6]. The unfavorable effect of large doses of alcohol is associated with the development and severe course of AH, cardiomyopathy, heart rhythm disorders. In women, the risk of NMI development increases at an alcohol dose 2 times lower than in men.

Excess body weight (body mass index more than 25 kg/m²) is associated with increased BP, disorders of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. Central obesity with abdominal fat deposition is particularly unfavorable for cardiovascular disease prognosis.

Central obesity is defined by the ratio of waist circumference to hip circumference. Central obesity is said to occur when this ratio is greater than 0.85 in women and greater than 1.0 in men. The best method of assessing body fat is to perform abdominal X-ray or magnetic resonance computed tomography.

Over the past 25 years, the number of overweight individuals in the European Union has increased 3-fold. Hormonal status. Changes in hormonal status are the most important factor influencing the risk of stroke in men and women.

Hormonal status in women. Early appearance of the first menstruation (menarche) in girls under 12 years of age increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and stroke [3,8]. A U-shaped relationship between the age of menarche and the risk of developing ICH was found in the UK Million Women Study. Women with menarche before the age of 10 years had a higher risk of stroke compared with women with menarche at the age of 13 years. However, women who had menarche at age 17 years or older also had a higher risk of stroke compared with women who had menarche at age 13 years [13].

Women of childbearing age, in contrast to men, have a low risk of developing ICH. However, after the onset of menopause, the probability of ICH development increases significantly. The results of clinical studies have established that the positive effect of estrogens in women is an increase in cardiac output, HDL-CS, fibrinolytic potential of blood, a decrease in total peripheral vascular resistance, a decrease in the formation of thromboxane A₂, the activity of components of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system of blood, LDL oxidation [6].

Pregnancy is a peculiar factor that increases the risk of ICH development. According to different authors, the incidence of stroke is 30 per 100,000 pregnant women [14]. Increase in estrogen levels during pregnancy leads to adaptive increase in platelet activity, increase in the content of blood coagulation factors, decrease in fibrinolysis and increase in procoagulant activity of endothelium [9].

The development of pregnancy complications (AH, diabetes mellitus, induced termination of pregnancy, habitual non-pregnancy, pre-eclampsia, preterm labour and low fetal weight at birth that does not correspond to the gestational age) indicates the presence of cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders, activation of haemostasis and endothelial dysfunction in a woman [5]. The most significant risk factors for both ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke are considered to be pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, which occur in 24-48% of women in late pregnancy [1, 6]. In recent years, the necessity

and safety of adequate antihypertensive therapy for AH in pregnancy have been substantiated [7]. In obesity, late age of first-born women, multiple pregnancies as a result of in vitro fertilization, NMIs develop in 40% of cases, and in 10-20 years the risk of AH increases 3-4 times, the risk of stroke, CHD, venous thrombosis and thromboembolism of the pulmonary trunk and pulmonary arteries 2 times [4,8]. A high risk of ischemic stroke during pregnancy and delivery is observed 2 days before delivery, on day 1 and within 6 weeks after delivery [9].

Oral contraceptives used in the 1970s contained more than 50 µg of estrogen and their use was associated with an increased risk of stroke, especially in women with AH and smokers. Combined contraceptives containing low doses of estrogen (less than 30 µg) currently in use are not risk factors for stroke, but this only applies to healthy women under 35 years of age who do not smoke and have normal BP. Migraine with aura at any age and migraine without aura over the age of 35 years increase the risk of stroke when using hormonal contraception by 7-10 times [11]. There is evidence that these drugs may increase susceptibility to venous thrombosis. This may occur predominantly in women with hereditary thrombophilia.

The climacteric period in women covers the period of time from 45 to 60 years and is characterised by the gradual cessation of menstrual function, and then the hormonal function of the ovaries against the background of general age-related changes in the body. To the premature development of menopause refers to the onset of menopause before 40-42 years of age, to late - after 55 years. There is evidence that early menopause (before 40 years of age), late menopause (after 55 years of age), and surgical menopause (bilateral ovariectomy performed at a young age) increase the risk of ICH [4].

One of the main protective factors in women in reproductive age is 17β-estradiol. Estradiol stimulates angiotensinogen formation in the liver, leading to increased aldosterone synthesis and sodium and water retention. These adverse effects of aldosterone are prevented by progesterone, which competitively binds to mineralocorticoid receptors in the kidneys. Estrogens increase nitric oxide and prostacyclin levels, decrease endothelin synthesis and thus contribute to the vasodilator effect. They also have antioxidant effects and reduce platelet functional activity. With the onset of menopause, the decrease in progesterone and estradiol is abrupt, while testosterone levels decrease slowly and smoothly [6]. Low estrogen levels are a trigger factor for a number of metabolic disorders (obesity, dyslipidemia, insulin resistance, etc.), united by the term "postmenopausal MS".

The imbalance of hormonal status causes the development of obesity with redistribution of fat to the upper half of the trunk [7]. Decreased levels of somatotrophic hormone also contribute to the progression of obesity. Somatotrophic hormone deficiency causes insulin resistance and hyperinsulinaemia. In insulin resistance, endothelial dysfunction occurs - the synthesis of endothelin 1, thromboxane and catecholamines increases, the level of nitric oxide and prostacyclin decreases, which causes the development of A.H. Hyperinsulinaemia leads to increased activity of the sympathetic nervous system and renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system [10].

Low levels of dehydroepi androsterone, an adrenal hormone involved in the synthesis of estrogens and testosterone, have been found to be associated with a high risk of ischemic stroke [14]. A number of epidemiological studies have found that hormone therapy with high estrogen content in healthy menopausal women increases the risk of ischemic stroke, myocardial infarction and A.H. Its use leads to activation of hemostasis and blood hypercoagulation. Estradiol increases the content of fibrinogen, blood clotting factors VII, VIII and X, and decreases the level of anticoagulants (antithrombin III, protein S). Using hormone replacement therapy increases the risk of stroke. According to the Women's Health Initiative study, the risk of stroke increases by 31% when combined hormone therapy is used and by 37% when estrogen is used [9].

Thus, factors that increase the risk of developing ICH in women include: early (≤ 10 years) or late (≥ 17 years) age of menarche; AH and gestational diabetes mellitus in pregnancy; pre-eclampsia and eclampsia; habitual non-pregnancy; preterm labor and fetal weight at birth not corresponding to gestational age; late onset of pregnancy; induced termination of pregnancy; multiple pregnancies; early (< 45 years) and late (> 55 years) age of menopause; low dihydroepiandrosterone levels; use of combined contraceptives or hormone replacement therapy (oral and transdermal forms of estrogen).

The onset of early menopause, natural or associated with surgery, increases the risk of cardiovascular disease 2-fold.

Hormonal status in men. Several retrospective studies examining gender differences in the incidence of stroke have demonstrated that men, compared with women, have a higher risk of developing stroke throughout most of their lives. Young and middle-aged men have a higher incidence of stroke. Above the age of 54 years, the incidence of stroke in men and women is similar [10]. Gender differences that are observed in young age are explained by differences in hormonal status and the protective role of estrogens in women, whose levels decrease dramatically after menopause.

The process of age-related changes in androgen status in men is accompanied by a decrease in testosterone levels. According to the Massachusetts study conducted in elderly men, the level of total testosterone begins to decline from 50-55 years of age by 0.8-1.6% per year. It is known that the physiological effects of testosterone are largely determined by its biologically active free fraction, and, therefore, the development of clinical manifestations of androgen deficiency is associated with a decrease in free testosterone. A significant contribution to the decrease in the level of biologically active testosterone fraction is made by sex steroid-binding globulin, the level of which increases with age [11]. In 2005, the International Society for the Study of the Aging Male (ISSAM) proposed the term "age-related hypogonadism".

Hypogonadism is diagnosed when the level of total testosterone is less than 12 nmol/l or free testosterone less than 225 pmol/l. The incidence of hypogonadism in men aged 40-49 years is 8%, 50-59 years - 29%, 60-69 years- 44%, over 70 years - 70% or more [13].

According to the 29-year prospective observational study Copenhagen City Heart Study [6,14], in the group of men with low testosterone levels (less than 10 nmol/l) the relative risk of ischemic stroke is 1.34, which in 21% of cases is associated with increased body mass index and in 14% - with AH.

Combination of risk factors. Often both men and women have several risk factors for acute MI, each of which may be expressed moderately. In this regard, the risk of acute MI, which may be high due to the mutual influence of factors, is determined by special scales based on the results of long-term follow-up of large cohorts. According to WHO data, when 1-2 factors occur, the risk of stroke development is 6%, 3 factors and more - 19%. The Framingham scale allows estimating the individual risk of stroke development (%) over the next 10 years.

Conclusions: Thus, the impact of gender differences on the course of stroke and recovery of impaired neurological function has been insufficiently studied to date. The most frequent gender differences in prognosis after stroke are explained by the fact that at the time of stroke women are usually older than men, have more risk factors and a wide range of comorbidities, reduced functional and cognitive status, and are more often socially isolated.

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